

A.C. Chronopotentiometry: A Theoretical Study of the Reversible Deposition of an Insoluble Substance*

N. P. BANSAL & H. L. JINDAL

Ramjas College, Delhi-7

Received 19 January 1972

Theoretical relationships for a.c. chronopotentiometry for the reversible deposition of an insoluble substance have been derived and compared with the corresponding case in conventional chronopotentiometry.

In chronopotentiometry, the variation of the potential of a polarised electrode during constant-current electrolysis of an unstirred solution of a depolariser, in presence of excess of a supporting electrolyte, is measured *versus* a depolarised reference as a function of time. Although, the applications of chronopotentiometry have been known since the early work of Weber¹, Sand² and Karaoglanoff³ and also of Butler and Armstrong⁴, active interest in application of this technique to analytical problems was taken only after the comprehensive work of Gierst and Juliard⁵ who also devised an ingenious experimental arrangement for oscillographic recording of potential-time curves. Mathematical relationships for various diffusion problems corresponding to specific electrode processes, have been worked out⁶ and applications to problems in analytical chemistry in aqueous⁷ and non-aqueous^{8,9} media have been recently reviewed. Superimposition of alternating current of constant amplitude on the constant direct electrolysis current (a.c. chronopotentiometry) greatly improves the precision in the transition time measurement. In this communication, we present the theoretical potential-time relationships for the reversible deposition of an insoluble substance using a.c. chronopotentiometry, which was needed for study of electrode processes in molten salts using a solid microelectrode; the mathematical relationship derived have been compared with the corresponding case in d.c. chronopotentiometry⁶.

Theoretical analysis: The flux of the reducible species (O_x) in this case will be a sum of direct current and alternating current components represented as

$$D_{O_x} \left[\frac{\partial C_{O_x}(x, t)}{\partial x} \right]_{x=0} = \frac{i + A \sin \omega t}{nFq} \quad [1]$$

where D_{O_x} is the diffusion coefficient of the species O_x , q the area of the electrode, A the amplitude of a.c. of frequency ω and i the constant d.c.; other terms having their usual significance. Applying the following initial conditions,

$$\begin{aligned} C_{O_x}(x, 0) &= {}^*C_{O_x} \\ C_{O_x}(\infty, t) &= {}^*C_{O_x} \end{aligned} \quad [2]$$

* Paper presented at the Convention of Chemists (1971) held at the Institute of Science, Bombay

where $*C_{Ox}$ is the uniform bulk concentration of Ox , and solving Fick's equation for linear diffusion, an expression for C_{Ox} at the electrode surface at a time 't' after the start of electrolysis is

$$C_{Ox}(o, t) - *C_{Ox} = - \frac{1}{nFqD_{Ox}^{\frac{1}{2}}} \left[\frac{2it^{\frac{1}{2}}}{\pi^{\frac{1}{2}}} + \frac{A}{\omega^{\frac{1}{2}}} \sin(\omega t - \pi/4) \right] \quad [3]$$

Assuming the activity of the deposit to be unity, the Nernst equation* is

$$E = E^0 + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln C_{Ox}(o, t)$$

where E is the electrode potential and E^0 is the standard potential of the metal ion-metal couple. Substitution of the value of $C_{Ox}(o, t)$ from (3) into Nernst equation gives :

$$E = E^0 + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \left[*C_{Ox} - \frac{1}{nFqD_{Ox}^{\frac{1}{2}}} \left\{ \frac{2it^{\frac{1}{2}}}{\pi^{\frac{1}{2}}} + \frac{A}{\omega^{\frac{1}{2}}} \sin(\omega t - \pi/4) \right\} \right] \quad [4]$$

Introducing the transition time, τ , given by Sand's equation⁶

$$\tau^{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{\pi^{\frac{1}{2}} nFq *C_{Ox} D_{Ox}^{\frac{1}{2}}}{2i} \quad [5]$$

(4) can be re-written as

$$E = E^0 + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \left[\frac{2i(\tau^{\frac{1}{2}} - t^{\frac{1}{2}})}{\pi^{\frac{1}{2}} nFq D_{Ox}^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right] + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \left[1 - \frac{k}{\tau^{\frac{1}{2}} - t^{\frac{1}{2}}} \sin(\omega t - \pi/4) \right] \quad [6]$$

where,

$$k = \frac{A\pi^{\frac{1}{2}}}{2i\omega^{\frac{1}{2}}}$$

Since,

$$E^0 + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \left[\frac{2i(\tau^{\frac{1}{2}} - t^{\frac{1}{2}})}{\pi^{\frac{1}{2}} nFq D_{Ox}^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right] = E_{dc} \quad [7]$$

Eqn. [6] can be re-written as

$$E = E_{dc} + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \left[1 - \frac{k}{\tau^{\frac{1}{2}} - t^{\frac{1}{2}}} \sin(\omega t - \pi/4) \right] \quad [7A]$$

where E_{DC} is the potential term obtained in d.c. chronopotentiometry involving the reversible deposition of an insoluble substance on an inert micro-electrode, the alternating component of the electrode potential ($E_{\sim}$) being

$$E_{\sim} = \left[\frac{RT}{nF} \ln \left[1 - \frac{k}{\tau^{\frac{1}{2}} - t^{\frac{1}{2}}} \sin(\omega t - \pi/4) \right] \right] \quad [8]$$

* In the reversible deposition of a *solid* on an inert microelectrode the activity of the deposit varies in the early stages of electrolysis, until the electrode is completely covered with at least a monolayer of the deposit. For an incompletely covered inert electrode, Nernst equation would not be applicable. In the above treatment the simplifying assumption is made that the activity of the deposit is unity.

DISCUSSION

Equation [7A] gives the electrode potential as a function of time in a.c. chronopotentiometry which consists of two components, $E_{a.c}$ and $E_{\sim}$, the latter arising due to the superimposed alternating current. It is seen that the alternating component of the potential has the same frequency as the current, but is $-\pi/4$ out of phase with respect to the latter. A plot of $E_{\sim}$ vs.

$$\ln \left[1 - \frac{k}{\tau^{\frac{1}{2}} - t^{\frac{1}{2}}} \sin(\omega t - \pi/4) \right]$$

at different values of t should be a straight line, its slope giving the value of n .

Significance of [8] at various values of t relative to τ are considered below :

Case I : when $t = 0$:

The value of $E_{\sim}$ at zero time ($t = 0$) is obtained by substituting $t = 0$ in eqn. [8]

$$[E_{\sim}]_{t=0} = \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \left[1 + \frac{k}{\sqrt{2\tau^{\frac{1}{2}}}} \right]$$

This can also be written in terms of the bulk concentration of substance O_x .

$$[E_{\sim}]_{t=0} = \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \left[1 + \frac{A}{nFq^*C_{0x}\sqrt{2D_{0x}^{\frac{1}{2}}\omega^{\frac{1}{2}}}} \right]$$

Since, $\frac{A}{nFq^*C_{0x}\sqrt{2D_{0x}^{\frac{1}{2}}\omega^{\frac{1}{2}}}} \ll 1$, on expanding the logarithmic factor and retaining only the first term, we get

$$[E_{\sim}]_{t=0} = \frac{RT}{n^2F^2q^*} \frac{A}{C_{0x}\sqrt{2D_{0x}^{\frac{1}{2}}\omega^{\frac{1}{2}}}}$$

Therefore, it is seen that $E_{\sim}$ at $t = 0$ is finite.

Case II :

At $0 \ll t \ll \tau$ and $\frac{k}{\tau^{\frac{1}{2}} - t^{\frac{1}{2}}} \sin(\omega t - \pi/4)$ smaller than unity, expanding the logarithmic factor of (8) and retaining only the first term, we have

$$\left[E_{\sim} \right]_{0 \ll t \ll \tau} = -\frac{RT}{nF} \cdot \frac{A\pi^{\frac{1}{2}}}{i\omega^{\frac{1}{2}}} \cdot \frac{\sin(\omega t - \pi/4)}{2(\tau^{\frac{1}{2}} - t^{\frac{1}{2}})}$$

This may be written as

$$\left[E_{\sim} \right]_{0 \ll t \ll \tau} = \left[\frac{dE_{a.c}}{dt} \right] t^{\frac{1}{2}} \cdot \frac{A\pi^{\frac{1}{2}}}{i\omega^{\frac{1}{2}}} \sin(\omega t - \pi/4)$$

Under these conditions, $E_{\sim}$ is thus seen to be proportional to

$$\left[\frac{dE_{d.c.}}{dt} \right] t^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad \frac{A}{i} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{1}{\omega^{\frac{1}{2}}}$$

Case III

At $t = \tau$, $[E_{\sim}]_{t=\tau}$ tends to infinity as can be seen from eqn. [8].

Calculated variations of $E_{\sim}$ for a hypothetical case is shown in Fig. 1; the corresponding curve for the variation of $E_{d.c.}$ (d.c. chronopotentiometry) is also plotted for comparison. It is seen (Fig. 1) from the $E_{d.c.}$ plot that there is a gradual rise in the potential-

Fig. 1: Calculated potential-time curves for a hypothetical case $*C_{ox} = 10^{-4}$ mole cm^{-3} ; $D_{ox} = 10^{-5}$ $\text{cm}^2 \text{sec}^{-1}$; $n = 1$; $i = 10^{-1}$ A; $\omega = 10^3$ cycles sec^{-1} ; $q = 1$ cm^2 .

time curve before the transition time. On the other hand, $E_{\sim}$ vs. time plot is almost horizontal and at the transition time it abruptly tends towards infinity. Hence the precision in the transition-time measurement by employing A.C. chronopotentiometry is greatly enhanced as compared to that in conventional chronopotentiometry.

REFERENCES

1. H. F. Weber, *Wied Ann. Physik*, 1879, **7**, 536.
2. H. J. S. Sand, *Phil. Mag.*, 1901, **1**, 45.
3. Z. Karaoglanoff, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1906, **12**, 5,

4. J. A. V. Butler and G. Armstrong, *Proc. Roy. Soc. (London)*, 1933, **A139**, 406; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1934, **30**, 1173.
5. L. Gierst and A. Juliard, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1953, **57**, 701.
6. P. Delahay, "New Instrumental Methods in Electrochemistry", Interscience Publishers Inc., New York, 1954.
7. D. G. Davis, "Electroanalytical Chemistry", Vol. I, A. J. Bard, (Ed.), Marcel Dekker Inc., New York, 1966.
8. H. C. Gaur and B. B. Bhatia, *J. Sci. Ind. Res. (India)*, 1962, **21A**, 16.
9. H. A. Laitinen and H. C. Gaur, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1958 **18**, 1

